

Chemistry of Bis-2'-Cyanoethyl Derivatives of some Aromatic Amines. Part III*. Some More Reactions of *p*-NN-Bis-2'-Cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde

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p-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde has been condensed with cyanacetamide, ethylacetate, acetophenone, rhodanine, nitromethane, *iso*-nicotinic acid hydrazide, hydantoin, thio-hydantoin and several acyl glycines and the products identified by both chemical and physical methods. Preliminary experiments on the use of the rhodanine derivative as a reagent for copper, mercury and silver and the aldehyde itself as a reagent for detecting acyl glycines by paper chromatography, have yielded encouraging results. *p*-NN-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzoic acid and *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene malonic acid and its *sec.* hydrazide have also been prepared.

The preparation and some of the reactions of *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde were reported earlier¹. This paper deals with the condensation of this aldehyde with ethylmalonate, ethylacetoacetate, acetophenone, nitromethane, cyanacetamide, rhodanine, hydantoin, thio-hydantoin, isonicotinic hydrazide and acyl glycines.

A study of these condensation reactions was taken up because of the many practical applications, the products may have. Some of these are briefly discussed here.

The use of *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine as analytical reagent for the quantitative estimation of some metals is well known^{2,3}. *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine, when treated with silver, cuprous and mercuric salts solution gave reddish violet, deep brown and light brown colour respectively. Detailed and systematic investigation to determine the optimum condition is in progress.

The marked hypoglycemic activity of certain hydantoin and thio hydantoin derivatives has been reported⁴. *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene hydantoin and thio-hydantoin prepared in the present work are being investigated for hypoglycemic activity.

A new paper strip test to determine the presence of isonicotinic hydrazide and *p*-aminosalicylic acid in the urine of tuberculosis patients who use these drugs, has been reported⁵. The reagent used is dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (DAB). Since *p*-NN-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde has a good deal of structural similarity to DAB, it was presumed that the former could also be used as a reagent for detecting these drugs. The aldehyde condensed readily with isonicotinic hydrazide but the colour of the product is not deep enough to make the aldehyde superior to DAB in this respect.

*Part II. O. P. Singhal, (Km.) Veena Gupta and P. I. Ittyerah, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1966, **29**, 69.

1. Abrahm Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah, *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 38.

2. F. Feigl, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1928, **74**, 380.

3. Organic Analytical Reagents by Welcher, Vol. III, p. 417; D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., New York.

4. S. S. Tewari and A. Swaroop, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 693.

5. R. C. R. Barreto and D. B. Mano, *J. Amer. Thoracic Soc.*, 1963, **4**, 556.

Acheson *et al*⁶ have prepared a number of oxazolones by condensing DAB and *p*-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde with acyl glycines and studied the possibility of using these aldehydes as reagents for the chromatographic detection of naturally occurring acyl glycines. Several oxazolones have now been prepared from *p*-*NN*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde and acyl glycines. Acetyl and phenacetyl glycines did not react under the conditions tried. The oxazolones obtained ranged from yellow to deep orange in colour and 40 to 65 percent in yield. The analytical results, melting point etc. are given in table I.

TABLE I

S. No.	Name	Formula	m p. °C.	Yield	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Required
1.	2-Phenyl-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	189	60	15.06	15.13
2.	2-Styryl-4-R'	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	221	55.5	13.95	14.14
3.	2-(<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	187	53.85	16.82	16.87
4.	2-(<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	235	38.56	16.93	16.87
5.	2-(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	252	57.7	16.85	16.87
6.	2-(3':5'-Dinitrophenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆	269	65.2	18.07	18.26
7.	2-(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	158	39.6	13.85	13.89
8.	2-(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	240	50.5	13.70	13.89
9.	2-(3':4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	292	59.2	13.65	13.59
10.	2-(<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl)-4-R'	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	248	62.5	13.92	14.00

R' stands for (*p*-*NN*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolone.

The methods adopted for condensation reactions were the usual ones and are stated briefly in the experimental section. For condensation of the aldehyde with acetophenone, resacetophenone and 5-bromo-resacetophenone, the method recommended by McOmie and Thatte⁷ was used, but only acetophenone condensed to give the expected chalcone. For condensing the aldehyde with nitromethane the procedure recommended by Merchant and Agrawal⁸ was adopted.

p-*NN*-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene ethylmalonate on mild hydrolysis gave the corresponding malonic acid and on treatment with hydrazine gave the secondary hydrazide.

The structures of a number of the products obtained have been confirmed by studying their I.R. spectra also. Thus the I.R. spectrum of the aldehyde shows one band at 1675 cm⁻¹ and another at 2250 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the -CHO and C=N groups respectively. The cyanacetamide product shows a band at 1680 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the -CONH₂ group and the secondary hydrazide the -NH- band at 3375 cm⁻¹. The rhodanine derivative has the >C=S band at 1190 cm⁻¹ and a band at 1620 cm⁻¹ indicating a -CH=C< group.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-*NN*-Bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde was prepared by the method recommended by Abraham Thomas and P. I. Ittyerah¹, using *NN*-bis-2'-cyanoethylaniline, phosphorus-oxy-chloride and dimethyl formamide. It melted at 118°C and the yield was 60.6%.

6. R. M. Acheson, D. A. Booth, R. Brettle and A. M. Harris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3457,

7. J. F. W. McOmie and S. D. Thatte, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 5298.

8. J. R. Merchant and S. R. Agrawal, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 472.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylamino-benzoic acid* was obtained by oxidising the aldehyde (1 g.) with potassium permanganate (4 g.) solution (50 ml.). The acid was precipitated by passing sulphur dioxide and purified by reprecipitation. It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 216° with slight decomposition, yield, 0.25 g. (22.7%).

Found: N, 17.12%; $C_{13}H_{13}N_3O_2$ requires N, 17.28%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene malonic acid* was prepared by passing steam for an hour through suspension of diethyl *p*-NN-*bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene malonate*¹ (1 g.) in a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate (10 ml.) and ethanol (5 ml.). A pale yellow precipitate obtained after acidifying the filtrate with hydrochloric acid, was purified by reprecipitation. The product was further purified by crystallisation from dilute ethanol and lustrous yellow plates melting at 193° (d) were obtained. Yield 0.4 g. (47.3%).

Found: N, 13.53%; $C_{16}H_{15}N_3O_4$ requires N, 13.42%.

The *secondary hydrazide* was obtained by gently refluxing a mixture of diethyl *p*-NN-*bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene malonate* (1 g.), hydrazine hydrate (0.2 g.) and ethanol (15 ml.; 50%) for an hour. After keeping the contents overnight and diluting with water, pale yellow crystals separated. It was washed well with hot ethanol; m.p. 220°; yield 0.5 g. (55.2%).

Found: N, 22.91%; $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_5$ requires N, 22.65%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene cyanacetamide* separated as a yellow crystalline product, heating equimolecular quantities of the aldehyde (0.57 g.) and cyanacetamide (0.21g.) in an oil bath at 125° for 4 hr. It was sparingly soluble in absolute alcohol and acetone, m.p. 265° (d); yield, 0.58 g. (79.8%).

Found: N, 23.45%; $C_{16}H_{15}N_5O$ requires N, 23.89%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene bis-ethylacetoacetate*. To a mixture of the aldehyde (1.1 g.) and ethylacetoacetate (1.3 g.) in absolute alcohol (5 ml.) was added half the quantity of piperidine (0.2 ml.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (2 ml.). After keeping at room temperature (20°) for 24 hr. the rest of the piperidine solution was added. The stout needle shaped crystalline product which separated was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol. It melted at 172°; yield 0.7 g. (30.5%).

Found: N, 8.778%; $C_{25}H_{31}N_3O_6$ requires N, 8.952%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylbenzylidene acetophenone* was obtained as a pale yellow crystalline product, when a mixture of aldehyde (1.1 g.), acetophenone (0.8 g.) and sodium hydroxide (1.2 g.) solution in alcohol (30 ml.) was stirred vigorously for 2 hr. at room temperature. The crude product was recrystallised from ethyl alcohol yielding pale yellow needles, m.p. 141°; yield, 0.9 g. (56.2%).

Found: N, 12.32%; $C_{21}H_{19}N_3O$ requires N, 12.76%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene rhodanine*. This was obtained on gently refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (1.1 g.), rhodanine (0.67 g.) and glacial acetic

acid for 1.5 hr. Recrystallisation from acetone afforded orange coloured plates, m.p. 243°; yield 0.95 g. (55.6%).

Found: N, 16.09%; S, 18.56%; $C_{16}H_{14}N_4OS_2$ requires N, 16.37%; S, 18.72%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylamino*- β -*nitrostyrene* was prepared by refluxing for 3 hr. a mixture of the aldehyde (1 g.), nitromethane (1 ml.), ammonium acetate (0.4 g.), and glacial acetic acid (5 ml.), in an oil bath kept at 135°. The dark red solid which separated was collected and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p., 211°; yield, 1 g. (83.3%).

Found: N, 20.36%; $C_{14}H_{14}N_4O_2$ requires N, 20.74%.

Iso-nicotinic acid hydrazone of p-NN-*bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzaldehyde*. This was obtained as a crystalline solid by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (0.55 g.), isoniazid (0.32 g.) and aqueous ethanol (10 ml.; 50%) for 2 hr. The crude product was purified by recrystallisation from a large volume of absolute alcohol, m.p., 225°; yield, 0.65 g. (75.3%).

Found: N, 23.98%; $C_{19}H_{18}N_6O$ requires N, 24.27%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene hydantoin*. A mixture of the aldehyde (1.14 g.), hydantoin (0.5 g.), ammonium acetate (0.4 g.), glacial acetic acid (2 ml.) and dry benzene (20 ml.) was refluxed for 2 hr. in a 50 ml. round bottomed flask attached to a Dean-Stark constant water separator. The yellow crystalline solid which separated out, was collected and recrystallised from acetone, m.p., 235°; yield, 1.2 g. (78%).

Found: N, 22.37%; $C_{16}H_{15}N_5O_3$ requires N, 22.65%.

p-NN-*Bis*-2'-*cyanoethylaminobenzylidene thio-hydantoin*. This was prepared by refluxing a mixture of the aldehyde (1.14 g.), thio-hydantoin (0.58 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.), glacial acetic acid (2.5 ml.) and two drops of acetic anhydride for 2 hr. in an oil bath kept at 160°. The dark red solid which separated, was collected and recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 231°, yield 0.95 g. (58.3%).

Found: N, 21.08%; S, 9.382%; $C_{16}H_{15}N_5SO$ requires N 21.54%; S, 9.895%.

5(4) *Oxazolones* :—The general method adopted for preparing the oxazolones is illustrated by the following example :

A mixture of the aldehyde (1.14 g.), hippuric acid (1.04 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.42 g.) and acetic anhydride (1.5 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. A clear brown solution was obtained within 15 mins. but soon the oxazolones separating out as orange plates. After cooling, ethanol (3 ml.) was added. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from acetone or ethyl acetate. Orange yellow needles of 2-phenyl-4 (*p*-NN bis-2'-cyanoethylaminobenzylidene)-5-oxazolone, yield 1.1 g. (60%), m.p. 189° were obtained.

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